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Analysis of labor resources and employment levels in the Russian Federation

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying the labor force and employment level lies in the possibilities for economic growth and development of effective strategies and policies. The aging of the population, the decline in the birth rate, and migration processes have a significant impact on the state of the workforce.

Materials and methods. The research materials consisted of data from periodicals focused on labor resources and employment in Russia, as well as statistical reporting materials from the Russian Federation and its constituent subjects.

Abstract, logical, monographic, computational-constructive, and comparative analyses, along with statistical methods, were employed in the research.

Results. Over the last decade, Russia experienced a decline in the total volume of labor resources, while the population employment rate increased. A positive trend is that the proportion of young people in the workforce is growing; however, the proportion of young people among the unemployed is also increasing, which hurts socio-economic processes, the demographic situation, and the country's economic growth.

Conclusion. Decrease in the working-age population hurts the country's economy. However, increased number of people younger than working age gives hope for replenishing the workforce in the future. The positive trend is employment growth which has a positive impact on the state's economic development. However, there are also negative aspects: a significant proportion of the unemployed in Russia are young people; this is a key factor slowing down the country's economic growth.

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INTRODUCTION

The study of labor resources and the population's employment level is essential; analysis of these indicators helps:

- assess the potential for economic growth;
- develop effective strategies and policies.

The state of the labor force is significantly influenced by such factors as population aging, declining birth rates, and migration processes. The employment level is directly related to the social well-being of citizens and the stability of society. It depends on how much people can provide for themselves and their families while also maintaining public order and security. Development of new industries, digitalization, and automation of production are changing the demand for certain professions and skills, and this requires employees to train and adapt to new conditions continually.

Production of goods and services requires two key components: material resources (such as raw materials, equipment, etc.) and human resources, specifically, workers with professional skills and knowledge. In this sense, labor resources as a part of the population act as a factor of economic development on a par with material resources.

Labor resources are a complex socio-economic category; they can serve as a measure of a society's labor potential and be used as a planned accounting indicator.

Definition of labor resources as an economic category is directly related to the conditions of labor reproduction established by the State. These conditions are the criteria for allocating labor resources from the total population and include, for example, working age limits, involvement of pensioners and people with disabilities in public production, duration of training and service in the army, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

M. V. Kurbatova and I. V. Donova note that measures to curb COVID-19 impacted labor markets which have since become the subject of special attention from researchers worldwide. The authors believe that government regulation contributed, on the one hand, to curbing employment decline and unemployment growth, and, on the other, to increasing the registered unemployment level [1].

E. S. Uzyakova confirms that labor efficiency is insufficient in conditions of low wages. According to the author, eliminating imbalances in the wage levels in

industries with the lowest labor productivity can lead to a 17.9% increase in overall labor productivity over the next five years [2].

E. S. Uzyakova examined the impact of employment level and dynamics in the informal sector on those of household incomes, labor productivity, and economic growth. According to the author, the labor productivity of informally employed individuals is 22-25% lower than that of personnel in organizations, and their withdrawal from the shadow economy could contribute to an increase in the total wage fund in 2020 by 6.8 billion rubles (including income tax) [3].

E. A. Edinak analyzes the influence of final demand and of a group of structural and technological factors on the employment dynamics in the Russian Federation based on an intersectoral balance. The author estimated the contribution of these factors to employment dynamics during recession (1991-1998), subsequent growth (1999-2014), and stagnation (2015-2017) [4].

A. O. Averyanov et al. analyze the current state of the labor market in Russia's most significant urban agglomerations. The authors note that the situation in the center of the agglomeration is generally better than in its periphery; however, there may be cases where various combined indicators, including job saturation and wages, reach an inversion where the center of the agglomeration lags behind its surroundings [5].

A. A. Zaytsev et al. propose a new approach to assessing aggregate labor productivity, which allows eliminating the significant impact of differences in economic structures on the final rating in inter-regional comparisons. The authors obtained a new picture of the state of productivity, which more accurately reflects the real level of efficiency of regional economies compared to the national level and in comparison with other federal districts [6].

A. N. Pilyasov & R. V. Goncharov analyze the patterns of distribution of Russia's productive forces that arise in connection with the innovative modernization of the national economy. The authors attribute the peculiarities of Russia's location to its low population density, extreme cold, significant under-urbanization, and lack of access to the sea. Approximately half of the country's territory does not have a "pronounced" close center, and Moscow has to play that role in innovative modernization and spatial reorganization. Modernization of Russia's spatial organization of productive forces, driven by common innovative trends, proceeds with significant specificity in large metropolitan agglomerations, cities with millions of inhabitants, old industrial areas, single-industry towns, and industrial-agricultural and agricultural territories [7].

D. A. Izotov and E. I. Motrich analyze the dynamics of spatial distribution, geographical structure, and the relationship between foreign labor and several macroeconomic parameters of the Far East's development from 2011 to 2016. According to the authors, the total number of foreign workers attracted to the Far Eastern regions was primarily determined by the size of their economy, indicating a gravitational connection between these parameters [8].

I. N. Dolgova et al. analyze labor market dynamics in the European part of the Russian Arctic regions, based on labor resource balance indicators available since 2013. The authors show that the trends in these regions are significantly more unfavorable compared to the country as a whole [9].

L. M. Nizova & E. N. Sorokina provide an analysis of the employment structure in the economy of the Republic of Mari El. The authors note the high degree of employment of graduates from educational organizations, as well as an increase in the proportion of citizens who have own businesses. The negative dynamics of employment, the imbalance of the professional cross-section of vacancies, and the professional qualification structure of the unemployed were also revealed [10].

V. N. Leksin notes that Russia developed intra-Russian and intra-regional labor migration. Among them, a significant place is occupied by the pendulum (daily departure to a place of work in another area) and shift labor organization (departure to a place of work for a long time due to the irrationality of daily return to a place of permanent residence). The concentration of shift work vacancies is noted in Moscow and several other large cities. In contrast, in sparsely populated areas of Russia, such vacancies are often found in stationary shift settlements [11].

K. A. Ustinova & S. V. Terebova separately consider the motives and incentives of the population engaged in creative work. The authors believe that workers in creative professions are distinguished from the rest of the population by their strong propensity for professional growth and self-realization, as well as their interest in adopting an innovative approach to work [12].

Modern economic systems are characterized by great flexibility and constantly changing requirements for the skill level of the workforce. The need for continuous knowledge updates and the continuity of the educational process are becoming key factors in ensuring labor market sustainability, according to A. Akaev et al., who suggest that countries that can cope with this structural challenge in a short time will

gain significant competitive advantages in the international markets of high-tech goods and services [13].

Further research is required on issues related to determining the potential of remote employment [14], international labor migration [15], contract employment [16], as well as measures to combat precarious employment [17], effective use of human resources of older people [18] and people of pre-retirement age [19].

Thus, the study and analysis of existing theories and models that explain the formation and utilization of labor resources enable an understanding of the principles and patterns underlying the labor market.

The collection and analysis of statistical data on the state of the labor force, the level of employment, and unemployment in Russia help identify trends, patterns, and features of the labor market.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials consisted of data from periodicals devoted to labor resources and employment in Russia (Regional Research of Russia, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Economic Change and Restructuring, etc.), as well as statistical reporting materials from the Russian Federation and its subjects.

Data from Rosstat (the Federal State Statistics Service of the Russian Federation) were utilized, including official statistics on employment, unemployment, workforce structure, and other relevant indicators.

Abstract, logical, monographic, computational-constructive, and comparative analyses, along with statistical methods, were employed in the research process.

RESULTS

The labor force is a subset of the population that, due to a combination of physical abilities, specialized knowledge, and experience, can participate in creation of material goods or work in the service sector.

The labor potential of a country refers to the labor force – the number of people who are of working age and employed before and after reaching this age. Men aged 15-65 and women aged 15-60 are considered able-bodied in Russia. Russia's labor force has declined in both absolute and relative numbers over the past decade: in 2010, there were 87.9 million people of working age (61.5% of the total population); by 2021,

the figure dropped to 83.2 million (57.2% of the total population). A similar decline is observed in the number of workers in Russia: the figures in 2010 and 2021 are 75.5 million people (52.8% of the total population) and 74.8 million people (51.4% of the total population), respectively. Notably, during the study period, a different picture emerges regarding employment and unemployment levels. There are positive trends: since 2010, the number of employed people has been 70 million (an employment rate of 92.7%), and by 2021, this figure increased to 71 million (an employment rate of 95%) (see Table 1) [20].

Table 1

Key labor market indicators in Russia for 2010-2021

	2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Population (at the end of the year), mil. people	142.9	146.6	146.8	146.9	146.8	146.8	146.2	145.5
including those:	87.9	84.2	83.2	82.3	81.4	82.7	81.9	83.2
of working age, mil. people	75.5	76.6	76.6	76.3	76.2	75.4	74.9	74.8
Number of workers, mil. people	70.0	72.3	72.4	72.3	72.5	71.9	70.6	71.0
including those:	5.5	4.3	4.2	4.0	3.7	3.5	4.3	3.8
employed, mil. people	92.7	94.4	94.5	94.8	95.2	95.4	94.3	95.0
unemployed, mil. people	7.3	5.6	5.5	5.2	4.8	4.6	5.7	5.0

The most essential characteristics of labor quality resources are gender, age structure, and the level of general and vocational education. The modern structure of the Russian labor force is characterized by a decrease in the proportion of working pensioners (65-70 years – 1.5%) and people of pre-retirement age (60-65 years – 4.6%), an increase in the proportion of young (20-40 years – 49%) and middle-aged people (40-50 years – 25%). Thus, the large number of young people in the Russian labor force creates favorable conditions for increasing labor productivity, which in turn leads to enhanced production efficiency and overall economic growth. Regarding the level of education in the workforce, people with higher education comprise 26%, secondary vocational education – 19% (combined – 45%). Naturally, the level is much lower than in developed countries but higher than the global average (25%).

The industry structure of the economy determines the professional structure of the workforce. The structure of employees by primary type of economic activity in Russia can be characterized by the following indicators: manufacturing – 13.8%,

construction – 8.7%, agriculture, forestry, hunting, fishing and fish farming – 6.6%, wholesale and retail trade – 18.5%, transportation and storage – 7.4%, public administration and military security – 5.1%, activities in the field of healthcare and social services – 7.7%, education – 6.2% (see Table 2).

Russia is facing an increase in the share of the population employed in non-industrial sectors, including utilities, consumer services, transport, education, healthcare, culture, art, science, scientific and information services, as well as management sectors; such growth is a global trend for developed countries. It is associated with an increase in labor productivity in branches of material production, as well as with the general socio-economic progress of society, including expansion of various public services. In Russia, this trend is primarily related to the economic crisis which led to the closure of numerous industrial enterprises, a shift in the economy's orientation towards importing industrial and agricultural goods from abroad, and a decline in foreign investment.

Table 2

Average annual number and structure of employees by primary type of economic activity in Russia in 2010-2021, mil. people

	2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total	70.0	72.3	72.4	72.3	72.5	71.9	70.6	71.0
Number of employees by type of economic activity: agriculture, forestry, hunting, fishing, and fish farming	6.1	5.5	5.5	5.1	4.9	4.8	4.6	4.7
mining	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.12	1.14	1.15	1.14	1.15
manufacturing	10.5	10.2	10.1	10.2	10.1	10	9.7	9.8
provision of electric energy, gas, and steam; air conditioning	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6
water supply, sanitation, waste collection and disposal, pollution control activities	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
construction	6.2	6.4	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.4	6.2	6.2
wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; transportation and storage	12.6	13.5	13.5	13.7	13.7	13.5	13.1	13.1
transportation and storage	5.1	5.3	5.3	5.2	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.3
activities of hotels and catering enterprises	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7

information and communication	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
activities, financial, and insurance	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4
activities related to real estate transactions, professional, scientific, and technical	1.8	2	2	2	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9
activities, administrative, and related additional services	2.9	3.1	3.1	2.9	2.9	2.8	2.7	2.8
public administration and military security; social security	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.8	1.9	2.0	1.9	1.9
activities in the field of health and social services	4	4	3.8	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.6	3.6
education	5.9	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.4	5.3	5.5
activities in the field of culture, sports, leisure, and entertainment	4.5	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4
provision of other types of services	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.4	1.2	1.2
	1.5	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.6

Another critical indicator of the effectiveness of labor resource utilization is the unemployment rate and its structure. The overall unemployment rate in Russia has decreased over the past decade from 7.3% in 2010 to 5% in 2021. Regarding the unemployment rate, undesirable trends are evident. Since the majority of the unemployed (59.4%) are young people (20-40 years old) (see Table 3).

In Russia, 28% of people aged 15-19 are unemployed. This figure among 20-24 year olds is 15.1%, 25-29 year olds – 5.8%, 30-40 year olds – 4%. This complicates demographic and socio-economic processes: due to the lack of resources, young people are unable to create families and have children. In the long run, this leads to a decline in the country's population replenishment by younger generations and a shortage of labor resources (see Table 4). As a result, labor productivity decreases in all areas of the economy, and the country's economic growth slows down.

Table 3

Structure of the unemployed by age group in Russia for 2010-2021, in %

Age groups	2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
15-19	5.9	4.7	4.2	3.8	3.9	3.3	3.5	3.4
20-24	20.8	19.8	19.1	17.9	18.5	17.6	18.1	18.8

25-29	15.0	16.1	16.5	16.4	16.0	16.0	16.0	15.9
30-34	11.7	12.7	13.1	13.1	13.6	14.4	14.2	14.0
35-39	9.6	10.3	10.8	10.7	11.1	11.0	10.8	10.7
40-44	8.5	8.8	9.0	9.3	9.4	9.6	9.5	9.3
45-49	10.5	8.1	7.9	8.4	8.3	9.0	8.9	8.9
50-54	10.1	10.4	9.8	9.4	8.8	8.8	8.8	8.1
55-59	5.7	6.4	6.4	7.4	6.9	6.8	6.9	7.7
60-64	1.7	2.2	2.4	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.2	2.1
65-69	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.9	0.8	1.0	1.0	1.0
70 and older	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.0	0.1	0.1

Table 4

Unemployment rate of the population by age group in Russia for 2010-2021, in %

Age groups	2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total	7.3	5.6	5.5	5.2	4.8	4.6	5.7	5.0
15-19	31.8	32.4	29.1	28.4	27.6	24.7	28.7	28.0
20-24	14.9	14.3	14.9	14.7	15.3	14.4	14.8	15.1
25-29	8.0	6.2	6.3	5.9	5.5	5.6	5.8	5.8
30-34	6.7	5.1	5.1	4.7	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4
35-39	5.8	4.5	4.6	4.1	3.9	3.6	3.6	3.6
40-44	5.6	4.1	4.0	3.9	3.5	3.4	3.5	3.5
45-49	5.7	4.0	4.0	3.9	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.6
50-54	5.8	4.5	4.3	4.1	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7
55-59	5.1	3.9	3.8	4.1	3.4	3.2	3.3	3.3
60-64	4.2	3.2	3.4	3.3	2.9	2.4	2.5	2.6
65-69	4.2	3.0	3.3	3.7	3.1	3.0	3.2	3.1
70 and older	2.5	1.8	2.1	2.0	1.6	2.4	2.3	2.2

DISCUSSION

Thus, analyzing current and future trends in the labor market helps determine which professions and skills will be in demand in the future [21]. This will enable the development of retraining and advanced training programs for employees, as well as of measures to attract young professionals to key sectors of the economy.

Development of new technologies such as artificial intelligence and robotics may lead to changes in the employment structure [22]. Research in this area will help understand which professions can be replaced by machines and which, conversely, will become more in demand.

The aging of the population, a decrease in the birth rate, and migration processes have a significant impact on the state of the workforce [23]. Studying these trends will allow us to predict future changes and develop measures to mitigate them.

Studying how changes in the global economy, trade wars, sanctions, and other factors [24] affect the international labor market, particularly in Russia, will help develop measures to minimize negative consequences and capitalize on new opportunities.

CONCLUSION

Decrease in the working-age population hurts the country's economy, but increase in the number of people younger than working age gives hope for replenishing the workforce in the future. Among the positive trends, notable highlights include employment growth and a decrease in unemployment, both of which have a positive impact on the state's economic development. However, there are negative aspects: a significant proportion of the unemployed in Russia are young people; this is a key factor slowing down the country's economic growth.

To improve the situation, the government is to develop and implement various incentive measures to motivate enterprises and organizations to hire young employees:

- discounts on insurance premiums;
- tax benefits;
- loans on preferential terms;
- other support measures for businesses and organizations that hire employees of a certain age.

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